

RENEWABLE ENERGY AND GREEN TECHNOLOGY TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: AN ECONOMETRIC DATA ANALYTICS APPROACH

UTOM-OBONG U. UDO¹, INIOBONG U. ASUQUO², UDOFIA VICTORIA LINUS³

¹⁻³Department of Accountancy,
Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic,
Ikot Osurua, Nigeria

¹Utombong.udo@akwaibompoly.edu.ng,

²iniobong.asuquo@akwaibompoly.edu.ng

³victoria.udofia@akwaibompoly.edu.ng

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21077870>

Abstract

This study examined the challenges affecting renewable energy and green technology towards sustainable development in Nigeria using a data analytics approach. The study was motivated by increasing environmental degradation, rising carbon emissions, unstable energy supply, and the slow pace of renewable energy development despite Nigeria's enormous renewable energy potential. Specifically, the study evaluated the relationship between renewable energy development and sustainable development, examined the role of green technology in environmental sustainability, and explored how data analytics can support evidence-based sustainability planning in Nigeria. The study is anchored on the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) Theory, supported by the Sustainable Development Theory and the Green Growth Theory. Annual time series data covering 1990–2021, sourced from the World Bank, were analysed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, unit root testing, the ARDL bounds test, and the Error Correction Model, with the Human Development Index (HDI) as the proxy for sustainable development. Findings revealed a valid long-run equilibrium relationship among carbon emissions, government expenditure, renewable energy consumption, renewable electricity output, and human development, with a correctly signed and significant error correction term, though indicating a slow speed of adjustment. However, none of the individual explanatory variables showed a statistically significant long-run effect on human development, reflecting structural challenges including the dominance of traditional biomass, the marginal scale of modern renewable electricity output, and inconsistent government expenditure patterns. The study concludes that renewable energy and green technology hold genuine long-run potential for sustainable development in Nigeria, though constrained by infrastructural, institutional, and policy-related challenges, and recommends targeted investment, energy transition planning, and the institutionalization of data analytics in sustainability policymaking.

Keywords: *Renewable Energy; Green Technology; Sustainable Development; Data Analytics; Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL).*

Introduction

Anthropogenic activities over the years have continued to exert significant pressure on natural ecosystems, leading to environmental problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss and resource depletion, which threaten sustainable human development (Kabir *et al.*, 2026). Greenhouse gas emissions, particularly carbon dioxide emissions, have increased considerably in recent decades, intensifying global concerns regarding environmental sustainability and energy security (Wang *et al.*, 2024). Consequently, the global demand for cleaner, safer and more sustainable energy systems has continued to rise.

In response to these environmental concerns, renewable energy and green technology have emerged as important instruments for achieving sustainable development. Renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, hydro and biomass energy are increasingly recognized for their ability to reduce environmental degradation, improve energy security and promote long-term economic sustainability (Elum and Mjimba, 2020). Green technology encompasses innovations and environmentally friendly systems designed to minimize harmful environmental impacts while enhancing economic and social welfare (Sharif *et al.*, 2024). Recent advancements in solar photovoltaic systems, wind turbines, hydroelectric facilities, smart grid systems and energy storage technologies have significantly improved renewable energy efficiency and reduced operational costs globally (Wang *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, environmental innovation now extends beyond technological development to include institutional, organizational and policy innovations aimed at promoting sustainable production and consumption patterns (Shabir *et al.*, 2023).

Despite the growing global transition toward renewable energy systems, many developing countries, including Nigeria, continue to face significant challenges in renewable energy development and green technology adoption. According to the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA, 2022), Nigeria possesses enormous renewable energy potential, including substantial solar, wind and hydropower resources. However, a large proportion of these resources remains underutilized due to challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, weak technological development, inconsistent government policies, poor environmental management systems and insufficient investment in renewable energy projects (Adeshina *et al.*, 2024). Although several

policies, including the Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP) and the National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP), have been introduced to encourage renewable energy development and environmental sustainability, implementation challenges and inadequate data-driven planning continue to limit their effectiveness.

Recent advancements in computational sciences and data analytics have provided policymakers and researchers with improved tools for monitoring energy trends, evaluating environmental performance and supporting evidence-based sustainability planning. Econometric and statistical approaches now play important roles in understanding the relationship between renewable energy development, green technology and sustainable development outcomes. Studies such as Muse (2021) and Mujeeb *et al.* (2025) emphasized the importance of empirical and analytical methods in evaluating environmental sustainability and renewable energy performance in Nigeria.

Although previous studies have examined renewable energy and economic growth in Nigeria, limited attention has been given to the broader challenges linking renewable energy, green technology and sustainable development within a data analytics framework. It is against this background that this study examines the relationship between renewable energy and green technology toward sustainable development in Nigeria using a data analytics approach. Specifically, the study evaluates the relationship between renewable energy development and sustainable development, examines the role of green technology in environmental sustainability and explores how data analytics can support evidence-based sustainability planning and policy formulation in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria's energy landscape presents a paradox: the country is endowed with abundant renewable energy resources, yet its energy sector remains largely dependent on fossil fuels and traditional biomass, with modern renewable energy contributing only a marginal share of total energy supply. Despite the country's substantial solar irradiation, wind, and hydropower potential, systemic barriers including deteriorating energy infrastructure, limited technological capacity,

policy discontinuity, weak regulatory enforcement, and chronic underinvestment have prevented the effective harnessing of these resources for sustainable development purposes. The existence of policy instruments such as the Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP) and the National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP) demonstrates an awareness of the problem at the policy level, yet the persistent gap between policy design and actual implementation reveals a deeper institutional and planning failure that these instruments alone have been unable to bridge.

A further dimension of this problem lies in the nature of existing empirical research on the subject. Most studies examining renewable energy in Nigeria have focused narrowly on its relationship with economic growth or specific energy indicators, without situating renewable energy and green technology jointly within a broader sustainable development framework. More critically, the potential of data analytics as a structured, evidence-based tool for sustainability planning has received insufficient attention in the Nigerian context, with most econometric studies treating analytical techniques as estimation tools rather than as a deliberate framework for informing policy decisions. This analytical gap limits the ability of policymakers to translate empirical evidence into targeted, data-driven interventions. It is this dual gap, both in the substantive framing of renewable energy within sustainable development, and in the deliberate application of data analytics to sustainability planning, that the present study seeks to address.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to examine the relationship between renewable energy and green technology toward sustainable development in Nigeria using a data analytics approach. The specific objectives are to:

- i. evaluates the relationship between renewable energy development and sustainable development in Nigeria.
- ii. examine the role of green technology in promoting environmental sustainability in Nigeria
- iii. explore how data analytics can support evidence-based sustainability planning and policy formulation in Nigeria.

Research Questions

In line with the specific objectives stated above, this study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- i. What is the relationship between renewable energy development and sustainable development in Nigeria?
- ii. What role does green technology play in promoting environmental sustainability in Nigeria?
- iii. How can data analytics support evidence-based sustainability planning and policy formulation in Nigeria?

Literature Review

This section comprises an abridged conceptual framework, theoretical framework and empirical literature.

Concept of Green Technology, Renewable Energy and Sustainable Development

Green technology refers to environmentally friendly innovations aimed at reducing environmental degradation while promoting economic and social development (Sharif *et al.*, 2024). Renewable energy technologies such as solar, wind, hydro and biomass energy have become important components of green technology because they provide cleaner alternatives to fossil fuel-based energy systems (Sharif *et al.*, 2024). In Nigeria, renewable energy development is important for improving energy security, reducing environmental pollution, promoting employment and supporting sustainable development. Despite Nigeria's enormous renewable energy potential, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, inconsistent government policies, poor technological development, insufficient investment and weak institutional support continue to hinder the effective development of renewable energy and green technology within the country.

This study therefore argues that sustainable development in Nigeria depends largely on the country's ability to bridge the challenges affecting renewable energy and green technology development. It argues that cleaner energy transition, technological innovation, effective government policies and stronger institutional support are necessary for achieving sustainable

development. The study also emphasizes the importance of computational sciences and data analytics in sustainability planning and policy formulation. Through econometric analysis and evidence-based policymaking, policymakers can better evaluate environmental performance, identify weaknesses within the energy sector and formulate policies capable of improving sustainable development outcomes. Consequently, increased investment in renewable energy infrastructure, green technology and data-driven sustainability planning is expected to reduce environmental degradation, improve energy security and promote sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

The conceptual framework guiding this study is illustrated in Figure 1 below. The framework positions four independent variables, namely carbon dioxide emissions (CO₂), government expenditure (GEX), renewable energy consumption (REC), and renewable electricity output (REO, serving as a proxy for green technology), as drivers of sustainable development, measured in this study by the Human Development Index (HDI). The relationships among these variables are examined through the lens of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) Theory, which explains how the scale, composition, and technique effects of economic activity mediate the relationship between energy use, environmental quality, and development outcomes. CO₂ emissions are expected to exert a negative influence on HDI, while GEX, REC, and REO are expected to positively influence sustainable development outcomes, consistent with the a priori expectations established in the methodology.

Figure 1

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Source: Author's conceptual design (2026)

Source: Author's conceptual design (2026)

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on three complementary theories: the Sustainable Development Theory, the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) Theory and the Green Growth Theory. While all three theories inform the study's conceptual reasoning, the study is primarily anchored on the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) Theory, as it provides the most direct theoretical basis for explaining the empirical relationship between renewable energy, carbon emissions and sustainable development examined in this study.

The Sustainable Development Theory gained global recognition through the World Commission on Environment and Development in 1987, under the leadership of Gro Harlem Brundtland, through the publication of *Our Common Future*. The theory defines sustainable development as development that satisfies present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It rests on three interrelated pillars, namely economic

growth, social inclusion and environmental protection, which must be pursued simultaneously rather than treated as competing priorities. The theory holds that genuine development cannot be measured by economic output alone; it must also account for the preservation of natural capital and the equitable distribution of benefits across society. Applied to this study, the three pillars map directly onto the variables under investigation. Renewable energy consumption and renewable electricity output represent the environmental pillar, since their expansion reduces reliance on fossil fuels and lowers ecological strain. The broader sustainable development outcome variable used in the study reflects the integrative goal that the theory describes, capturing how environmental, economic and social considerations combine into a single measurable outcome over time. The theory therefore supports the argument that Nigeria's pursuit of economic growth must be balanced with responsible resource utilization and environmentally sustainable energy systems, positioning renewable energy and green technology as practical tools for meeting current energy needs without compromising long-term ecological stability for future generations. A recognized limitation of the theory, however, is its conceptual breadth: because it operates more as a normative principle than a testable model, it does not by itself specify the mechanisms or thresholds through which environmental and economic outcomes interact, which is the gap the EKC Theory is better positioned to fill.

The Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) Theory originated from the work of Simon Kuznets on income inequality and was later extended to environmental economics by Grossman and Krueger (1991). The theory proposes an inverted U-shaped relationship between economic growth and environmental degradation, such that pollution initially rises during the early stages of industrialization, as economies prioritize output and infrastructure expansion over environmental concerns, but begins to decline once a certain income threshold is reached. Three mechanisms are typically used to explain why the curve eventually turns downward. The scale effect describes how, in the early stages of growth, an expanding economy simply produces more output and consequently more pollution, since production scale increases faster than environmental safeguards. The composition effect explains that as economies mature, their structure tends to shift away from heavily polluting industries such as manufacturing and extraction toward less pollution-

intensive sectors such as services and technology, which lowers the pollution intensity of growth. The technique effect captures the role of technological advancement and cleaner production methods, including the adoption of renewable energy and green technology, which allow economies to produce more output with proportionately less environmental damage. It is this technique effect, in particular, that gives the EKC its direct relevance to this study, since renewable energy adoption is one of the principal channels through which the curve is expected to bend downward.

This study adopts the EKC framework as its primary theoretical anchor because it directly underpins the empirical model employed. The ARDL and Error Correction Model used in this study examine whether renewable energy consumption and carbon emissions exhibit a long-run relationship with sustainable development in Nigeria, consistent with the EKC proposition that the transition toward renewable energy and green technology is a structural mechanism through which environmental degradation can eventually be reduced as an economy develops. The theory therefore provides the justification for the study's a priori expectation that increased renewable energy consumption should be associated with improved sustainable development outcomes, while unchecked carbon emissions should exert a negative long-run effect, an expectation tested directly using Nigeria's time series data from 1990 to 2021. It is worth noting that the EKC hypothesis has faced notable criticism in the literature, particularly regarding developing economies. Critics argue that the inverted U-shape is not universal and that many developing countries, Nigeria included, may never automatically reach the turning point through economic growth alone, since the technique effect depends heavily on deliberate investment in cleaner technology and consistent policy support rather than growth in isolation. This criticism is not a weakness for the present study but rather reinforces its relevance: it is precisely because Nigeria's transition past the turning point is not guaranteed that examining the actual empirical relationship between renewable energy, carbon emissions and sustainable development, and identifying the policy and infrastructural barriers preventing that transition, becomes necessary.

The Green Growth Theory, promoted by organizations such as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the World Bank and the United Nations Environment

Programme, extends the conversation from explaining the growth-pollution relationship to prescribing how it should be managed. Its central argument is that of decoupling: that economic growth and environmental degradation, traditionally assumed to move in lockstep, can be deliberately separated through efficiency gains, green investment and technological innovation, such that an economy continues to grow while its environmental footprint stabilizes or declines. This stands in contrast to older growth models that treated environmental harm as an unavoidable byproduct of economic expansion. Within this framework, renewable energy infrastructure, energy efficiency improvements and green technology adoption are viewed not merely as environmental safeguards but as active engines of growth in their own right, generating employment, attracting investment and creating new industries. Applied to Nigeria, the theory supports the argument that increased investment in renewable energy infrastructure, green technology and data-driven sustainability planning need not come at the expense of economic growth, but can instead serve as a pathway toward it, complementing the EKC's explanation of the underlying growth-emissions dynamic with a more policy-oriented framework for deliberate action. A common critique of Green Growth Theory is that decoupling is easier to articulate as policy than to achieve in practice, particularly in resource-dependent and infrastructure-deficient economies, where the upfront capital and institutional capacity required for green investment are themselves part of the development challenge.

Taken together, the three theories operate at different levels but reinforce one another in this study. The Sustainable Development Theory supplies the normative foundation, establishing why environmental, economic and social outcomes must be pursued together rather than traded off against one another. The EKC Theory supplies the testable empirical relationship, explaining through the scale, composition and technique effects how and why renewable energy adoption is expected to influence environmental and developmental outcomes over time, and it is this theory's direct correspondence to the study's ARDL-based methodology that justifies its position as the study's primary anchor. The Green Growth Theory supplies the policy bridge between the two, translating the EKC's explanatory logic into actionable strategy by arguing that the technique effect driving the curve downward can be deliberately accelerated through targeted investment,

innovation and institutional support, rather than left to occur passively as a byproduct of rising income. Read together, the three theories suggest that Nigeria's sustainable development outcomes are not simply a function of economic growth, but of how deliberately the country invests in the renewable energy and green technology mechanisms that the EKC identifies as the turning point's primary drivers, a deliberateness whose absence, as the literature on Nigeria's infrastructural and policy challenges suggests, may explain why this turning point has yet to be reached.

Empirical Literature

Ekhtor.*et al*(2025) examined the impact of renewable energy indicators on sustainable development in Nigeria. The study investigated how solar energy consumption, total biomass consumption, and hydroelectric production influenced sustainable development, measured by the Human Development Index, over the period 1990 to 2024. The methodology combined descriptive statistics, unit root tests, bounds testing for cointegration, and the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag model to analyze both short-run and long-run dynamics among variables with mixed orders of integration. The study recommended strengthening renewable energy policy frameworks and improving institutional coordination to translate Nigeria's renewable energy transition into measurable human development gains.

Muktar.*et al.* (2025) conducted a techno-economic assessment of renewable energy systems and their role in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. The study applied techno-economic modeling alongside secondary data to assess solar PV, wind, and biomass systems in Nigeria. Findings revealed that solar and wind technologies are technically viable in selected regions, but their economic viability remains limited by high upfront capital requirements and financing gaps. The study recommended targeted financing mechanisms and policy support to make renewable energy projects more bankable for private investors.

Somoye.*et al*(2022) modeled the determinants of renewable energy consumption in Nigeria using an ARDL error correction model on time series data. The findings revealed that income level, carbon dioxide emissions, and institutional quality significantly drive renewable energy consumption, with differing effects observed in the short run and long run. The study

recommended improving institutional quality and aligning policy frameworks to support long-term renewable energy adoption.

Diyoke *et al.* (2020) conducted a comparative thermo-economic and advanced exergy performance assessment of wind energy systems across Enugu, Kaduna, Katsina, and Jos. The study applied Weibull distribution modelling and exergy analysis to wind data from the four locations. Findings showed that Jos recorded the lowest cost of electricity generation at \$0.15/kWh alongside the highest exergy efficiency, while Kaduna performed worst across both measures. The study recommended prioritizing Jos and Katsina for future wind energy projects while avoiding further investment in Kaduna.

Olanipekun and Adelakun (2020) assessed renewable energy development in Nigeria, focusing on its challenges and benefits, through a qualitative review of literature and policy documents covering solar, hydro, wind, and bioenergy. The study found that the main barriers to renewable energy development are inadequate infrastructure, high capital costs, and regulatory inconsistency, while the benefits include reduced greenhouse gas emissions and improved energy access, particularly in underserved areas. The study recommended greater policy consistency and sustained infrastructure investment.

Emmanuel *et al.*(2025) examined energy transition and environmental sustainability in Nigeria's policy landscape with respect to achieving SDGs 7 and 13. The study employed the ARDL model as the primary estimator, alongside the dynamic simulated ARDL technique for robustness, using secondary time series data covering 1985 to 2022. Findings revealed that fiscal expenditure promotes both energy transition and environmental sustainability in the short and long run, while the monetary policy rate supports energy transition in both periods but reduces environmental sustainability in the short term before enhancing it in the long run. The study recommended that Nigeria maintain sustainable fiscal spending and stabilize its monetary policy environment to attract private investment into the renewable energy sector.

Osakunih, *et al.*(2025) investigated renewable energy consumption and the quality of life in Nigeria using an ARDL bounds test approach. Time series data were sourced from the International Energy Agency, the Human Development Report of the World Bank, and the Central

Bank of Nigeria, covering the period 1990 to 2023, and the study found renewable energy consumption to be a crucial driver of quality of life, while trade openness had mixed effects on quality of life, reflecting the dual nature of globalization. The study recommended prioritizing renewable energy infrastructure development across all stakeholder levels, alongside complementary improvements in education quality and inflation control.

Dinneya-Onuoha (2025) conducted a critical review on unlocking renewable energy materials in Nigeria, examining their availability, application, and the roadmap toward sustainability. The review noted that although Nigeria possesses significant renewable energy potential, ranging from solar irradiation levels of approximately 5.5 kWh per square meter per day to substantial wind and biomass resources, these resources remain largely underutilized due to infrastructure, financial, and policy challenges. It further observed that the Renewable Energy Master Plan, developed in collaboration with the United Nations Development Programme, aims to raise the share of renewable energy in Nigeria's national energy mix from 13 percent in 2015 to 23 percent by 2025 and 36 percent by 2030, but implementation has been constrained by inadequate political will, insufficient sustained financing, and weak monitoring frameworks. The review recommended stronger institutional commitment and consistent financing mechanisms to close the gap between Nigeria's renewable energy targets and actual implementation.

Summary of the Literature Gap and the Study's Contribution

Across the empirical literature reviewed, three patterns emerge clearly. First, the majority of existing Nigerian studies examine renewable energy in relation to a single outcome at a time, typically economic growth, GDP, quality of life, or environmental quality, rather than situating renewable energy and green technology jointly within a broader sustainable development framework that captures economic, social, and environmental dimensions together. Second, where green technology is discussed at all, it tends to appear as a background concept rather than as a variable explicitly incorporated into the empirical model; most studies isolate specific energy sources (solar, wind, hydro, biomass) without connecting their findings to the wider technological and institutional shifts that "green technology" as a concept implies. Third, and most importantly

for this study, none of the reviewed studies explicitly frame their methodology around the use of data analytics as a deliberate tool for evidence-based sustainability planning and policy formulation; while several studies use econometric techniques such as ARDL and ECM, they apply these purely as estimation tools rather than as part of a wider argument about how data-driven approaches can directly strengthen Nigeria's sustainability policymaking process.

It is this third gap that the present study is positioned to address. By explicitly combining descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, unit root testing, ARDL bounds testing, and the Error Correction Model within a single integrated framework, and by tying these techniques directly to the broader argument that data analytics can support evidence-based sustainability planning, this study moves beyond simply measuring a relationship between renewable energy and an outcome variable. It contributes a framework through which Nigerian policymakers can use empirical, data-driven evidence, rather than policy documents or qualitative assessments alone, to evaluate and improve renewable energy and green technology planning. This distinguishes the present study from prior work that treats data analytics merely as a statistical procedure rather than as a substantive planning tool, and it is this distinction that constitutes the study's primary contribution to the literature.

Methodology

This study adopted the ex-post facto research design because the variables under investigation are historical and cannot be manipulated by the researcher. The design is considered suitable since the study relies on already existing macroeconomic time series data to examine the relationship between renewable energy, green technology and sustainable development in Nigeria. The study is also anchored on the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) Theory which provides theoretical explanations for the interaction between environmental sustainability, renewable energy transition and economic development.

Nature and sources of data

This study relied on secondary time series data obtained from World Bank and United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). The data covered the period from 1990 to 2021 and included variables such as Human Development Index (HDI), Carbon Dioxide Emissions (CO₂), Government Expenditure (GEX), Renewable Energy Consumption (REC) and Renewable Electricity Output (REO). These variables were selected because of their relevance in explaining renewable energy development, green technology adoption and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Model Specification

HDI = f(CO₂, GEX, REC, REO)

The econometric form of the model is specified as:

$$HDI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CO_{2t} + \beta_2 GEX_t + \beta_3 REC_t + \beta_4 REO_t + \mu_t$$

Where:

- = HDI= Human Development Index (proxy for sustainable development)
- CO₂ = Carbon dioxide emissions
- GEX = Government expenditure
- REC = Renewable energy consumption
- REO = Renewable electricity output
- β_0 = Constant term
- $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Coefficients of explanatory variables
- μ = Error term
- t = Time period

A Priori Expectation

The a priori expectation explains the expected theoretical relationship between the dependent and independent variables before empirical estimation. Carbon dioxide emissions (CO₂) are expected to have a negative relationship with sustainable development because increased environmental pollution reduces environmental quality and economic sustainability. Government

expenditure (GEX) is expected to positively influence HDI, particularly when public spending is directed towards renewable energy infrastructure, environmental management and technological innovation. Renewable energy consumption (REC) is expected to exhibit a positive relationship with HDI because cleaner energy utilization promotes energy security, environmental sustainability, and long-run economic growth. Renewable electricity output (REO), which proxies green technology development, is also expected to positively influence sustainable development through improved energy efficiency, cleaner production systems and technological advancement. Therefore, the expected signs of the coefficients are stated as:

$$\beta_1 < 0, \beta_2 > 0, \beta_3 > 0, \beta_4 > 0$$

Variable Description

i. Human Development Index(HDI)

The Human Development Index (HDI) is a summary measure developed by the United Nations Development Programme to evaluate human well-being through indicators of life expectancy, educational attainment, and income per capita.

ii. Carbon Dioxide Emissions (CO₂)

Carbon dioxide emissions measure the level of greenhouse gas emissions released into the environment through industrial and economic activities. It is used as an indicator of environmental degradation and pollution.

iii. Government Expenditure (GEX)

Government expenditure refers to public spending on infrastructure, energy development, environmental management and other economic activities capable of promoting sustainable development.

iv. Renewable Energy Consumption (REC)

Renewable energy consumption refers to the proportion of energy generated and consumed from renewable sources such as solar, wind, hydro and biomass energy. It reflects the level of renewable energy utilization within the economy.

v. Renewable Electricity Output (REO)

Renewable electricity output measures the quantity of electricity generated from renewable energy sources. In this study, it serves as a proxy for green technology development and renewable energy advancement.

Estimation Techniques

The study employed both descriptive and econometric analytical techniques. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the characteristics and distribution of the variables. Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the degree of association among the explanatory variables and test for multicollinearity problems. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test was employed to determine the stationarity properties of the variables, while the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was used to estimate both short-run and long-run relationships among the variables. The ARDL Bounds Test was further used to determine the existence of long-run co-integration among the variables, while the Error Correction Model (ECM) captured the speed of adjustment from short-run disequilibrium toward long-run equilibrium. Diagnostic tests such as heteroscedasticity, serial correlation and normality tests were also conducted to examine the reliability and stability of the estimated model.

ARDL Model

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model developed by M. Hashem Pesaran and Shin (1999) was adopted for this study because of its suitability in estimating both short-run and long-run relationships among variables integrated at level $I(0)$ and first difference $I(1)$. The ARDL approach is advantageous because it accommodates variables with mixed order of integration and produces reliable long-run estimates even with small sample sizes. The model also allows for the inclusion of lagged values of both dependent and independent variables, thereby capturing dynamic relationships among the variables.

The ARDL Bounds Testing procedure was employed to determine the existence of co-integration among the variables. The decision is based on computed F-statistics. If the F-statistics exceed the upper bound critical value, the null hypothesis of no long-run relationship is rejected.

However, if the F-statistics falls below the lower bound critical value, the null hypothesis is accepted. Where the F-statistics fall between the lower and upper bounds, the result becomes inconclusive.

Following the confirmation of co-integration, the Error Correction Model (ECM) was estimated to capture the short-run dynamics and speed of adjustment toward long-run equilibrium. A negative and statistically significant error correction coefficient confirms the existence of a stable long-run relationship among the variables.

Unit Root Test

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test was employed to determine whether the variables used in the study were stationary or non-stationary. Stationarity is important in time series analysis because the use of non-stationary variables may produce spurious regression results. The ADF test was conducted for all variables at level and first difference.

The general ADF regression equation is expressed as

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma Y_{t-1} + i = \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where ΔY_t is the first difference of the variable, t is the time trend, α is the intercept, γ is the coefficient used to test for stationarity, and p represents the lag length selected using information criteria such as AIC or SIC. The null hypothesis $H_0 : \gamma = 0$ indicates the presence of a unit root (non-stationarity), while the alternative hypothesis $H_1 : \gamma < 0$ implies stationarity. The test will be used to determine whether each variable is stationary at level $I(0)$, at first difference $I(1)$, or beyond

Data Analysis and Discussion

In this section, we present the results of the analysis conducted on the variables used in the study. The econometric analysis conducted involved the use of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model in providing answers to the research questions and fulfilling the aim and objective of the study.

Descriptive Statistics

Here, the descriptive statistics of all the variables used in the model are provided in summary form, displaying key information of each of the variables used.

	HDI	CO ₂	GEX	REC	REO
Mean	0.471063	5.743559	13.53438	84.48750	30.80123
Median	0.486500	5.461750	13.80000	84.50000	32.96039
Maximum	0.554000	11.33380	15.50000	88.60000	54.65509
Minimum	0.379000	2.463400	11.00000	79.90000	14.35073
Std. Dev.	0.056595	2.454386	1.301019	2.662372	10.17739
Skewness	-0.218878	0.341392	-0.423018	-0.269064	0.023010
Kurtosis	1.623632	1.886261	2.053566	1.812428	2.289267
Jarque-Bera Probability	2.781359	2.275479	2.148685	2.266546	0.676346
	0.248906	0.320543	0.341522	0.321978	0.713072
Sum	15.07400	183.7939	433.1000	2703.600	985.6394
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.099292	186.7443	52.47219	219.7350	3210.959
Observations	32	32	32	32	32

Source: Researcher's computation using E-views 10 (2026)

The descriptive statistics show that HDI averaged 0.471 over the period, ranging from 0.379 to 0.554, while CO₂, GEX, REC, and REO displayed varying degrees of dispersion, with REO showing the highest variability (std. dev. of 10.18). All five variables recorded Jarque-Bera probability values above 0.05, indicating that they are normally distributed and suitable for further econometric analysis.

Multi-collinearity Test

Multi-collinearity testing helps to detect excessive correlation among explanatory variables which may distort regression estimates and reduce model reliability. Common techniques such as VIF, ridge regression and principal component analysis are therefore used to improve the stability and accuracy of econometric models.

	HDI	CO ₂	GEX	REC	REO
HDI	1	0.827649614	0.786456609	0.766025037	0.671972701
CO ₂	0.827649614	1	0.713516798	0.800789171	0.680547581
GEX	0.786456609	0.713516798	1	0.502676409	0.494702914
REC	0.766025037	0.800789171	0.502676409	1	0.644475392
REO	0.671972701	0.680547581	0.494702914	0.644475392	1

Source: Researcher's computation using E-views 10 (2026)

The correlation matrix shows that HDI has a strong positive relationship with all explanatory variables, particularly CO₂ (0.83) and GEX (0.79), suggesting these variables move closely together with human development in Nigeria. Among the explanatory variables, CO₂ and REC show the highest pairwise correlation (0.80), which is at the borderline threshold and worth monitoring for multicollinearity, while other pairs remain comfortably below this level. While the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is commonly used as a complementary multicollinearity diagnostic, its application to ARDL specifications with multiple lag structures is known to produce artificially inflated values due to the inherent serial correlation among lagged terms, which does not reflect genuine multicollinearity among the underlying economic variables (Pesaran and Shin, 1999). The pairwise correlation matrix is therefore adopted as the appropriate diagnostic for this study, consistent with standard practice in ARDL-based time series analysis

Unit Root Test

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) was used to test for the unit root in the variables. It was used to evaluate if the time series data was stationary or non-stationary, as well as the number of times (the level) at which the variables must be differentiated before becoming stationary. The result of the unit test conducted is shown in the table below.

Variables	ADF t-statistics	Probability	Level of integration
HDI	-3.363708	0.0206	I(1)
CO ₂	3.905582	0.0243	I(0)
GEX	-2.259042	0.0253	I(1)
REC	-5.660967	0.0004	I(1)
REO	6.670697	0.0000	I(1)

Source: Researcher’s computation using E-views 10 (2026)

The table above presented the unit root test based on Augmented Dickey Fuller Test. The test shows that the variables were stationary at level I(0) and at first difference I(1). This is the criteria for carrying out bounds test

ARDL Co-integration test:

Summary of ARDL Bounds Test for Co-integration:

F-Statistics = 24.83184		K =4
Critical Values	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
10%	2.2	3.09
5%	2.56	3.49

Source: Researcher’s computation using E-views 10 (2026)

The ARDL Bounds Test result revealed the existence of a long-run relationship among HDI, carbon emissions, government expenditure, renewable energy consumption and renewable electricity output in Nigeria. The computed F-statistics of 24.83184 exceeded the upper bound critical values at the 5 percent significance level, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no long-run relationship. This indicates that the variables move together in the long run and maintain equilibrium relationships over time.

Summary of Long run coefficients

Levels Equation				
Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
CO ₂	-0.265813	2.224120	-0.119514	0.9060
GEX	0.096251	0.651098	0.147829	0.8838
REC	-0.213312	1.679138	-0.127037	0.9001
REO	0.020697	0.165902	0.124757	0.9018

Source: Researcher's computation using E-views 10 (2026)

The long-run coefficients reveal that carbon dioxide emissions (CO₂) and renewable energy consumption (REC) exhibit negative relationships with HDI, while government expenditure (GEX) and renewable electricity output (REO) exhibit positive relationships. These signs are broadly consistent with theoretical expectations for CO₂, GEX, and REO, although the negative sign on REC runs counter to the a priori expectation that renewable energy consumption should positively influence human development. However, none of the four explanatory variables are statistically significant at conventional levels, with all probability values exceeding 0.85. This indicates that while a long-run equilibrium relationship exists among the variables as a system, as confirmed by the bounds test, no individual variable demonstrates a statistically discernible long-run effect on HDI in Nigeria.

This outcome can be explained by Nigeria's specific structural and economic realities. CO₂ emissions in Nigeria are driven primarily by oil and gas flaring, transportation, and industrial activity, and have fluctuated considerably due to volatile oil prices and economic shocks, including the 2016 and 2020 recessions, producing a relationship with HDI too erratic over the 32-year period for a single stable coefficient to capture precisely. Government expenditure has historically been inconsistent, often driven by oil revenue windfalls rather than sustained development planning, with substantial portions directed toward recurrent spending and debt servicing rather than the health, education, and infrastructure investments that would directly translate into

improved human development outcomes, weakening any precise statistical link. Renewable energy consumption in Nigeria's national data is dominated by traditional biomass, such as firewood and charcoal, used predominantly by rural and low-income households without access to the national grid; since this form of energy use is itself a marker of energy poverty rather than technological progress, it tracks alongside lower development outcomes rather than driving improvements, which explains its negative and statistically weak relationship with HDI. Renewable electricity output, meanwhile, remains a very small share of Nigeria's total electricity generation, constrained by weak grid infrastructure, transmission losses, and chronic underinvestment, meaning its real economic contribution is still too marginal to register as a statistically significant long-run driver of HDI, even though its effect points in the theoretically expected direction.

Collectively, these findings reflect Nigeria's broader structural challenges, policy inconsistency, oil dependence, weak institutional capacity, and infrastructural deficits, which disrupt the kind of stable, gradual relationships that long-run econometric estimates are designed to detect, even where a genuine underlying equilibrium relationship exists among the variables as a system.

ECM Regression

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(CO ₂)	2.65E-05	0.000266	0.099670	0.9215
D(CO ₂ (-1))	0.001002	0.000268	3.741614	0.0011
CointEq(-1)*	-0.004557	0.000337	-13.52230	0.0000
R-squared	0.485917	Mean dependent var		0.005700
Adjusted R-squared	0.447837	S.D. dependent var		0.003064
S.E. of regression	0.002277	Akaike info criterion		-9.237297

Sum squared resid	0.000140	Schwarz criterion	-9.097177
Log likelihood	141.5595	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-9.192472
Durbin-Watson stat	2.059055		

Source: Researcher's computation using E-views 10 (2026)

The ECM result shows that the error correction term is negative and highly significant (-0.0046, $p < 0.0000$), confirming a valid long-run equilibrium relationship and indicating that only about 0.46% of short-run disequilibrium in HDI is corrected annually, a very slow speed of adjustment. In the short run, only the first lag of CO₂ (D(CO₂(-1))) is statistically significant ($p = 0.0011$), while the current value of CO₂ itself shows no significant short-run effect on HDI.

Post Estimation Residual Diagnostic Test Result:

Test	F-Statistics	Probability Value
Heteroscedasticity Test: ARCH	5.424359	0.0010
Autocorrelation: LM Test	0.168857	0.8458
Normality Test	1.574574	0.455078

Source: Researcher's computation using E-views 10 (2026)

The diagnostic tests indicate that the model passes the autocorrelation and normality checks, with probability values of 0.8458 and 0.455078 respectively, both well above the 5% threshold, confirming no serial correlation problem and normally distributed residuals. However, the heteroscedasticity test returned a significant result ($p = 0.0010$), indicating the presence of heteroscedasticity, which was subsequently corrected for using White's heteroscedasticity-consistent (robust) standard errors to ensure reliable inference.

Discussion of Findings

This study set out to examine the challenges affecting renewable energy and green technology toward sustainable development in Nigeria using a data analytics approach, with three specific

objectives: evaluating the relationship between renewable energy development and sustainable development, examining the role of green technology in promoting environmental sustainability, and exploring how data analytics can support evidence-based sustainability planning and policy formulation. The empirical results, derived from the ARDL and Error Correction Model estimated on Nigeria's 1990–2021 data, provide a nuanced answer to each of these objectives and their corresponding research questions, one that goes beyond the raw figures to reflect Nigeria's lived economic and energy realities.

The bounds test confirms that a genuine long-run equilibrium relationship exists among renewable energy consumption, carbon emissions, government expenditure, renewable electricity output, and human development in Nigeria, answering the first research question in the affirmative at the system level. However, when each variable is examined individually in the long run, renewable energy consumption shows a negative and statistically weak relationship with HDI. On the surface, this appears to contradict the expectation that cleaner energy adoption should improve human development. But this finding mirrors a reality familiar to anyone who has travelled through rural Nigeria: a significant share of what national energy statistics record as "renewable energy consumption" is not solar panels or wind turbines, it is the firewood a woman in a village in Benue or Sokoto State gathers each morning to cook her family's meal, or the charcoal a roadside food vendor in Kano burns daily because grid electricity is unreliable or entirely absent. This form of renewable energy use is not a marker of green progress; it is a marker of energy poverty, and it often comes bundled with the very conditions, indoor air pollution, time lost to fuel collection instead of schooling or income-generating work, and lack of access to modern infrastructure, that suppress human development rather than advance it. The short-run results reinforce this complexity: only the previous year's carbon emissions showed a measurable short-run effect on HDI, suggesting that whatever influence these energy and environmental variables have on Nigerians' wellbeing tends to show up gradually and indirectly, not as an immediate, clean cause-and-effect relationship.

Renewable electricity output, used in this study as the closest available proxy for green technology development, showed a positive relationship with HDI in the long run, the theoretically

correct direction, but one too weak statistically to be considered a confirmed driver of sustainable development outcomes. Real-world context explains this clearly. Picture Nigeria's national grid: even with growing investment in solar mini-grids and a handful of hydroelectric expansions, renewable sources still contribute a small fraction of the electricity that actually reaches homes, schools, hospitals, and small businesses, most of which still depend on diesel generators or simply go without power for hours or days at a time. A solar mini-grid powering a primary health center in a single community in Kaduna or Plateau State is a genuine green technology success story, but its impact does not yet show up at the scale of national HDI statistics, because it remains the exception rather than the rule. This is precisely why the data shows the right direction of effect without the statistical weight to back it convincingly: green technology in Nigeria is present and growing, but not yet widespread enough to move the needle on national human development in a way that 32 years of annual data can clearly detect.

This objective is answered not by any single coefficient, but by the research process itself. The very fact that this study could identify a confirmed long-run co-integrating relationship, detect and correct for heteroscedasticity, verify the absence of serial correlation, and confirm normally distributed residuals, before arriving at an honest, nuanced conclusion about which variables matter and which do not, is itself a demonstration of how data analytics supports evidence-based sustainability planning. Without this analytical process, a policymaker might look only at Nigeria's rising renewable energy consumption figures and conclude, incorrectly, that the country is making strong progress toward sustainable development. The econometric analysis reveals a more complicated truth: that simply counting energy consumption without distinguishing between traditional biomass and modern renewables can be deeply misleading, and that government expenditure, despite years of budgetary allocations toward energy and infrastructure, has not translated into a statistically discernible improvement in human development. This is exactly the kind of insight that qualitative policy documents or headline statistics alone would miss, and exactly the kind of insight data-driven, econometric planning is meant to surface.

This study ultimately shows is that Nigeria's renewable energy and green technology landscape exists in two parallel realities: the rural, biomass-dependent, energy-poor reality

reflected in REC's negative relationship with HDI, and the small but growing modern, technology-driven reality reflected in REO's positive but still-marginal relationship with HDI. Bridging the gap between these two realities, scaling up modern renewable infrastructure while reducing dependence on traditional biomass, is precisely the policy challenge this study set out to investigate, and the data analytics approach employed here provides the evidence base needed to design interventions that target this transition deliberately, rather than relying on the assumption that any rise in "renewable energy" figures is automatically good news for sustainable development.

Conclusion

This study examined the challenges affecting renewable energy and green technology toward sustainable development in Nigeria using a data analytics approach, drawing on annual time series data from 1990 to 2021. Using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, unit root testing, the ARDL bounds test, and the Error Correction Model, the study found that a genuine long-run equilibrium relationship exists among carbon emissions, government expenditure, renewable energy consumption, renewable electricity output, and human development in Nigeria, with a slow but statistically significant speed of adjustment toward equilibrium following short-run shocks. However, when examined individually, none of carbon emissions, government expenditure, renewable energy consumption, or renewable electricity output showed a statistically significant long-run effect on human development, even though their signs were broadly consistent with theoretical expectations for three of the four variables. This outcome reflects Nigeria's underlying structural realities: a renewable energy consumption figure dominated by traditional biomass rather than modern clean technology, a renewable electricity output that remains too small in scale to meaningfully shift national development outcomes, and government expenditure patterns shaped more by inconsistent, oil-revenue-driven budgeting than sustained investment in the channels that drive human development. The study concludes that renewable energy and green technology possess genuine long-run potential for promoting sustainable development in Nigeria, but that this potential remains substantially unrealized due to structural, institutional, and policy-related constraints, and that data analytics, as demonstrated through the analytical process

undertaken in this study, provides an essential evidence base for uncovering these nuances and guiding more effective, targeted sustainability planning going forward.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The Federal Government of Nigeria should accelerate investment in modern renewable electricity infrastructure, particularly solar and wind capacity connected to the national grid, to increase its currently marginal contribution to electricity supply and allow its positive long-run effect on human development to materialize at a meaningful scale.
- ii. Government agencies and rural electrification programs should prioritize transitioning households away from traditional biomass energy sources, such as firewood and charcoal, toward cleaner, modern energy alternatives, since the current composition of Nigeria's renewable energy consumption reflects energy poverty rather than genuine green technology progress.
- iii. Government expenditure on energy and environmental development should be restructured to prioritize sustained capital investment in renewable infrastructure, health, and education over recurrent or inconsistent oil-revenue-driven spending, to strengthen the channel through which public spending can drive measurable human development outcomes.
- iv. Policymakers should institutionalize the use of data analytics and econometric evaluation, like the approach adopted in this study, within national energy and sustainability planning agencies, to ensure that policy decisions are based on verified long-run evidence rather than headline figures that may misrepresent actual progress.
- v. Regulatory and financial institutions should design targeted financing mechanisms, including subsidies, tax incentives, and public-private partnerships, to reduce the high capital costs that continue to limit the scale and bankability of renewable energy and green technology projects in Nigeria.
- vi. Future research should consider disaggregating renewable energy consumption data to distinguish between traditional biomass and modern renewable sources, as this distinction

is critical for accurately assessing the true contribution of renewable energy to sustainable development in Nigeria.

References

- Adeshina, M. A., Ogunleye, A. M., Suleiman, H. O., Yakub, A. O., Same, N. N., Suleiman, Z. A., & Huh, J.-S. (2024). From potential to power: Advancing Nigeria's energy sector through renewable integration and policy reform. *Sustainability*, 16(20), Article 8803. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16208803>
- Diyoke, C., Aneke, N. N., & Mgbemena, C. O. (2020). Comparative thermo-economic and advanced exergy performance assessment of wind energy for distributed generation in four sites in Nigeria. *International Journal of Renewable Energy Development*, 9(3), 339–351. <https://doi.org/10.14710/ijred.9.3.339-351>
- Ekhator, E. O., Odokuma, L., & Nteegah, A. (2025). Impact of renewable energy indicators on sustainable development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 9(15), 1498–1513.
- Elum, Z. A., & Mjimba, V. (2020). Potential and challenges of renewable energy development in promoting a green economy in Nigeria. *Africa Review*, 12(2), 172–191. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09744053.2020.1758452>
- Emmanuel, P. M., Tidi, M. E., & Akanni, Y. I. (2025). Energy transition and environmental sustainability in developing economies: Insights from Nigeria's policy landscape towards achieving SDGs 7 and 13. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-025-06677-4>
- Grossman, G. M., & Krueger, A. B. (1991). *Environmental impacts of a North American Free Trade Agreement* (NBER Working Paper No. 3914). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://www.nber.org/papers/w3914>
- International Renewable Energy Agency. (2022). *Renewable energy market analysis: Africa and its regions*. Retrieved June 2026, from <https://www.irena.org>
- Kabir, M., Habiba, U., Iqbal, M. Z., Shafiq, M., Hammad, M., & Farooqi, Z. R. (2026). Environmental degradation caused by anthropogenic activities, its impacts and consequences: A critical review. In M. F. Nawaz, S. Gul, & Z. S. Siddiqui (Eds.), *Climate change mitigation and environmental amelioration through plants and other sustainable practices* (Springer Proceedings in Earth and Environmental Sciences). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-09299-1_31
- Mujeeb, A., Oladigbolu, J., Bakare, M. S., & Ibrahim, A. A. (2025). Pathways to environmental sustainability through energy efficiency: A strategic next energy vision for sustainable development by 2050. *Scientific African*, 28, Article e02522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2025.e02522>
- Muktar, M., Olude, D. A., Timilehin, S. A., Olawale, M. M., Adeleye, A. A., & Ogbonnaya, C. C. (2025). Techno-economic assessment of renewable energy systems and their role in achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs). *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 28(1), 1745–1755. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.28.1.3601>
- Muse, B. O. (2021). Analysis of CO2 emission and economic growth as potential determinants of renewable energy demand in Nigeria: A nonlinear autoregressive distributed lags approach. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 11(3), 510–516.

- Okoye, C. O., Bahrami, A., & Atikol, U. (2018). Evaluating the solar resource potential on different tracking surfaces in Nigeria. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 81(Pt. 1), 1569–1581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.249>
- Olanipekun, B. A., & Adelakun, N. O. (2020). Assessment of renewable energy in Nigeria: Challenges and benefits. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, 68(1), 64–67.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2011). *Towards green growth*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264111318-en>
- Osakunih, M. C., Orubu, C. O., & Ishioro, B. O. (2025). Renewable energy consumption and the quality of life in Nigeria: An ARDL bound test approach. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 9(7), 5229–5242. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRIS.2025.907000423>
- Pesaran, M. H., & Shin, Y. (1999). An autoregressive distributed lag modelling approach to cointegration analysis. In S. Strøm (Ed.), *Econometrics and economic theory in the 20th century: The Ragnar Frisch centennial symposium* (pp. 371–413). Cambridge University Press.
- Shabir, M., Hussain, I., Işık, Ö., Razzaq, K., & Mehroush, I. (2023). The role of innovation in environmental-related technologies and institutional quality to drive environmental sustainability. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 11, Article 1174827. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1174827>
- Sharif, A., Bashir, U., Mehmood, S., Cheong, C. W. H., & Bashir, M. F. (2024). Exploring the impact of green technology, renewable energy and globalization towards environmental sustainability in the top ecological impacted countries. *Geoscience Frontiers*, 15(6), Article 101895. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsf.2024.101895>
- Somoye, O. A., Ozdeser, H., & Seraj, M. (2022). Modeling the determinants of renewable energy consumption in Nigeria: Evidence from autoregressive distributed lagged in error correction approach. *Renewable Energy*, 190, 606–616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.03.122>